

Competency Statements

Supplementary Material for Master Thesis: Development of a
Master-level Program for Green Coding: A Curriculum Design and
Implementation Approach

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Introduction: This file contains a set of competency statement used in the
aforementioned Master thesis. The competency statements are grouped into the
courses of the finished curriculum and presented within the next sections.

1 Sustainability and Software

Competency Title	Effects of Human Actions on the Environment
Competency Statement	Evaluate direct and indirect environmental impacts of human behaviour in order to recommend strategies that reduce impacts such as emissions, resource depletion, and waste.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Social Issues and Professional Practice	Analyse
Ethical and Intercultural Perspective	Understand
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Futures-Thinking	Apply
Values-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Proactive, Purpose-driven, Responsible	

Table 1: Competency Framework Extension – Effects of Human Actions on the Environment

Competency Title	Importance of Sustainability
Competency Statement	Internalize importance of sustainable actions and foster intrinsic motivation to continue sustainable practices.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Ethical and Intercultural Perspective	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Futures-Thinking	Evaluate
Values-Thinking	Evaluate
Dispositions	
Purpose-driven, Passionate, Proactive	

Table 2: Competency Framework Extension – Importance of Sustainability

Competency Title	Effects of ICT Sector on the Environment
Competency Statement	Comprehend the effects of production, use, and disposal of hardware and software connected to the ICT sector.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Digital Design	Understand
Circuits and Electronics	Understand
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
System Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Proactive, Purpose-driven, Responsible	

Table 3: Competency Framework Extension – Effects of ICT Sector on the Environment

Competency Title	Risks of Sustainability
Competency Statement	Comprehend and identify pitfalls of sustainability, e.g. Greenwashing or Rebound Effect.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Evaluate
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Futures-Thinking	Understand
Values-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Meticulous, Responsible, Purpose-driven	

Table 4: Competency Framework Extension – Risks of Sustainability

2 Introduction to Green Coding

Competency Title	Structure and Component Comprehension
Competency Statement	Understand complex relations and structures in order to connect different components of an overarching topic.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Enterprise Architecture	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Systems-Thinking	Create
Futures-Thinking	Understand
Strategic	Understand
Integration	Apply
Dispositions	
Adaptable, Meticulous, Self-directed	

Table 5: Competency Framework Extension – Structure and Component Comprehension

Competency Title	Software Ecosystem
Competency Statement	Place software products in a landscape and system and understand their connections and interferences.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
System Analysis and Design	Evaluate
Software Modeling and Analysis	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
System Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Adaptable, Meticulous, Inventive	

Table 6: Competency Framework Extension – Software Ecosystem

Competency Title	No Single Source of Truth in Green Coding
Competency Statement	Comprehend the complexity of Green Coding and accept that many issues do not have a single source of truth but rather different approaches that must be weighed and compared.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Create
Quality Assurance / Control	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Purpose-driven, Proactive, Self-directed	

Table 7: Competency Framework Extension – No Single Source of Truth in Green Coding

Competency Title	Analysis of Dynamic and Evolving Fields
Competency Statement	Analyse dynamic and changing fields in order to stay on top of fast evolving topics, such as energy prices.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Create
Research and Self-Starter / Learner	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Futures-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Purpose-driven, Proactive, Self-directed	

Table 8: Competency Framework Extension – Analysis of Dynamic and Evolving Fields

3 Green Computing

Competency Title	Green Software Development
Competency Statement	Comprehend the environmental impact of choices in programming (e.g. algorithms, programming languages) and how their substitution could affect the environmental impact of software.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Programming Languages	Apply
Programming Fundamentals	Apply
Data Structures, Algorithms and Complexity	Apply
Problem Solving and Trouble Shooting	Evaluate
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Implementation	Apply
Dispositions	
Adaptable, Meticulous, Self-directed	

Table 9: Competency Framework Extension – Green Software Development

Competency Title	Network Structures
Competency Statement	Understand, inspect, and create data transfer networks in order to assess energy hotspots or diversions.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Data and Information Management	Understand
Computer Networks	Understand
Digital Design	Understand
Software Design	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Implementation	Apply
Dispositions	
Adaptable, Meticulous	

Table 10: Competency Framework Extension – Network Structures

Competency Title	Web Development
Competency Statement	Understand components of the internet in general and websites in particular.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Data and Information Management	Understand
Computer Networks	Understand
Digital Design	Understand
Graphics and Visualization	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Implementation	Apply
Dispositions	
Inventive, Responsible, Responsive	

Table 11: Competency Framework Extension – Web Development

Competency Title	Artificial Intelligence
Competency Statement	Comprehend the core concepts, working methods, and areas of application of artificial intelligence systems in order to assess their environmental and social impacts.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Intelligent Systems	Understand
Security Issues and Principles	Remember
Ethical and Intercultural Perspective	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Apply
Futures-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Inventive, Meticulous, Purpose-driven	

Table 12: Competency Framework Extension – Artificial Intelligence

4 Green Software Development Life Cycle

Competency Title	Green Software Design
Competency Statement	Analyse existing systems and software regarding their design and architectural choices to enhance sustainability.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Systems Analysis and Design	Create
Software Design	Create
Problem Solving and Trouble Shooting	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Implementation	Apply
Dispositions	
Inventive, Meticulous, Adaptable	

Table 13: Competency Framework Extension – Green Software Design

Competency Title	Requirements Engineering
Competency Statement	Include sustainability into requirements in the planning phase of the software engineering process.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Requirements Analysis and Specifications	Create
Collaboration and Teamwork	Apply
Multi-Task Prioritization and Management	Apply
Relationship Management	Evaluate
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Apply
Futures-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Proactive, Collaborative, Responsible	

Table 14: Competency Framework Extension – Requirements Engineering

Competency Title	Agile Project Management
Competency Statement	Plan and execute projects in a structured, agile way to efficiently manage teams and roles.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Software Process	Evaluate
Collaboration and Teamwork	Apply
Multi-Task Prioritization and Management	Apply
Project and Task Organization and Planning	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Proactive, Collaborative, Responsible	

Table 15: Competency Framework Extension – Agile Project Management

Competency Title	Life Cycle Thinking
Competency Statement	Broaden horizon when conceptualizing new projects to include not just present-day issues but also past and future thinking.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Evaluate
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Apply
Systems-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Adaptive, Inventive, Purpose-driven	

Table 16: Competency Framework Extension – Life-Cycle Thinking

5 Awareness and Sustainability in HCI

Competency Title	Software Quality Assessment
Competency Statement	Inspect existing software in regards to their software quality on basis of relevant standards and sustainability aspects.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Software Quality, Verification and Validation	Evaluate
Software Design	Understand
Quality Assurance / Control	Analyse
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Professional, Purpose-driven, Meticulous	

Table 17: Competency Framework Extension – Software Quality Assessment

Competency Title	Usability and Accessibility of Software
Competency Statement	Comprehend the importance of inclusivity and accessibility of software and how to enhance them in new and existing projects.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Software Quality, Verification and Validation	Understand
Software Design	Apply
Quality Assurance / Control	Analyse
User Experience Design	Create
Graphics and Visualization	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Inventive, Meticulous, Adaptable	

Table 18: Competency Framework Extension – Usability and Accessibility of Software

Competency Title	Digital Sobriety and Wellbeing
Competency Statement	Comprehend and convey the importance of a responsible approach to digital products and services in order to conceptualize and develop meaningful software products.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Apply
Ethical and Intercultural Perspectives	Evaluate
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Intra-personal / Self-Awareness	Create
Values-Thinking	Apply
Futures-Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Purpose-driven, Responsible, Proactive	

Table 19: Competency Framework Extension – Digital Sobriety and Wellbeing

Competency Title	Self-Improvement
Competency Statement	Understand the necessity to constantly check one’s own work and change it if necessary in order to integrate sustainability into work practices.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Apply
Research and Self-Starter / Learner	Create
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Intra-personal / Self-Awareness	Create
Dispositions	
Inventive, Meticulous, Adaptable	

Table 20: Competency Framework Extension – Self-Improvement

6 Sustainability and Governance in Companies

Competency Title	Integrate Sustainability into Existing Structures
Competency Statement	Propose and implement the expansion of an established system to ensure the integration of sustainability into existing company structures.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Social Issues and Professional Practice	Evaluate
Quality Assurance / Control	Create
Collaboration and Teamwork	Apply
Strategic	Apply
Interpersonal	Apply
Integration	Create
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
System Thinking	Apply
Dispositions	
Professional, Responsive, Passionate	

Table 21: Competency Framework Extension – Integrate Sustainability into Existing Structures

Competency Title	Motivating and Poignant Communication
Competency Statement	Capture and motivate an audience by communication with passion and poignancy and yet professionally in both oral and written form.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Oral Communication and Presentation	Apply
Written Communication	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Passionate, Proactive, Professional	

Table 22: Competency Framework Extension – Motivating and Poignant Communication

Competency Title	Change Management
Competency Statement	Understand the difficulties change brings for employees and meet them with compassion, patience, and resilience.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Collaboration and Teamwork	Create
Oral Communication and Presentation	Apply
Relationship Management	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Strategic	Apply
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Passionate, Proactive, Professional	

Table 23: Competency Framework Extension – Change Management

Competency Title	Governance and Legal Frameworks
Competency Statement	Comprehend and apply basic legal language and frameworks in order to reach a company's governance goals.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Quality Assurance / Control	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Strategic	Understand
Dispositions	
Meticulous, Responsible, Professional	

Table 24: Competency Framework Extension – Governance and Legal Frameworks

7 Current Trends in Green Coding

Competency Title	Independent Research
Competency Statement	Connect academic resources in order to gather a holistic overview of a topic.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Social Issues and Professional Practice	Understand
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Evaluate
Research and Self-Starter / Learner	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Self-directed, Purpose-driven, Meticulous	

Table 25: Competency Framework Extension – Independent Research

Competency Title	Literature Quality Assessment
Competency Statement	Inspect publications and other resources in regards to their quality and reliability.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Analytical and Critical Thinking	Evaluate
Research and Self-Starter / Learner	Apply
Multi-Task Prioritization and Management	Apply
Project and Task Organization and Planning	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Values-Thinking	Understand
Dispositions	
Meticulous, Proactive, Self-directed	

Table 26: Competency Framework Extension – Literature Quality Assessment

Competency Title	Presentation
Competency Statement	Present complex and theoretical topics in a structured and captivating way.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Oral Communication and Presentation	Create
Time Management	Apply
Project and Task Organization and Planning	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Passionate, Proactive, Self-directed	

Table 27: Competency Framework Extension – Presentation

8 Green Coding in Practice

Competency Title	Collaborative Project Management
Competency Statement	Break down problems into tasks and distribute them fairly and according to individual competencies collaboratively in a team.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Project Management	Create
Multi-Task Prioritization and Management	Apply
Collaboration and Teamwork	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Collaborative, Professional, Responsive	

Table 28: Competency Framework Extension – Collaborative Project Management

Competency Title	Individual Project Management
Competency Statement	Break down problems into tasks individually, allot appropriate time, and ensure the meeting of deadlines.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Project Management	Create
Multi-Task Prioritization and Management	Apply
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Intra-personal or Self-Awareness	Apply
Dispositions	
Passionate, Proactive, Responsible	

Table 29: Competency Framework Extension – Individual Project Management

Competency Title	Teamwork
Competency Statement	Show openness, patience, and helpfulness in collaborative projects to ensure a harmonic and productive work environment.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Collaboration and Teamwork	Create
Relationship Management	Apply
Dispositions	Proactive, Passionate, Responsible
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Proactive, Collaborative, Responsible	

Table 30: Competency Framework Extension – Teamwork

Competency Title	Status Quo Assessment
Competency Statement	Inspect and assess the current situation in an organization or company accurately and holistically in order to gain insights into possible impediments or improvements.
Knowledge Element	Skill Level
Social Issues and Professional Practice	Evaluate
Collaboration and Teamwork	Apply
Relationship Management	Understand
Sustainability Competency	Skill Level
Interpersonal	Apply
Dispositions	
Collaborative, Meticulous, Responsible	

Table 31: Competency Framework Extension – Status Quo Assessment